

Figure 3f shows data belonging to 3 independent experiments: Experiment 1, Experiment 2 and Experiment 3. BglG:mRFP signal from samples expressing MP:GFP-SL relative to BglG:mRFP from samples expressing MP:GFP for each fraction (IN, FT and IP) was averaged and SD determined.

Experiment 1

BglG:mRFP SL-tagged/non-tagged mRNA

	IN	FT	IP
Av	1,16	0,76	2,99
SD	0,17	0,43	1,04

Av, average; SD, standard deviation

Experiment 2

Experiment 3

